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A Study of attitude of Urdu Medium teachers towards CAI programme in Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh

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Introduction

All the aspects of human life are witnessing impact of computers. Computers are being used in education since, 1960 and the advent of micro computers in 1970s increased its usage in education. There are different uses of computers in education like for teaching, learning, data storage, administration, research and evaluation etc. The use of computers in teaching has lot of potential in the form use of computer assisted instruction in schools.

The need and significance of the study is evident from the following. It is a common observation that the Urdu medium schools are ill-equipped as far as the academic and infrastructural facilities are concerned. The lack of qualified teachers and further lack of latest technologies and training of teachers in use of latest developments affects directly and indirectly on student community. Hence, there is a need to fill this vacuum and the initiative can be taken up in the form of use of computer assisted instruction. Some of the teachers feel that the use of computers is interference, impediment in their work and computers try to replace classroom teacher but this is actually no so. The CAI programmes are just a supplementary effort and hence, teachers' attitude has to be known.

The study involves all the teachers who were involved in the project intended to know the effectiveness of CAI on school children. The study involved government, private (aided) schools, boys,

girls and hence, their respective teachers were part of the study. The study could be extended to Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh as the teachers were involved from both the states.

Some of the limitations of the study include that the study was limited to the teachers involved in the study, it was limited to only the science teachers, it has limitations in the form number of subject, geographic locations and also the study was limited to Urdu medium teachers only.

Statement of the Problem

The Urdu school teachers like any other school teachers have a craze for use of computers in schools. Efforts were not made to know their attitude in previous studies too. This has refrained the planners and policy makers away from planning CAI programmes. Hence, the investigators planned to make a study of attitude of Urdu medium teachers towards CAI programme in Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh.

Operational definition of terms used in the study

Attitude towards CAI

This is a predisposition or tendency of Urdu medium teachers to respond positively or negatively towards use of computer assisted instruction in schools.
Urdu Medium Teachers

The high school teachers who are teaching science subject in Urdu medium schools.

Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI)

This is content based, self-learning, structured, offline computer programme, involving teaching in a programmed instructional format. This uses a combination of text, graphics, sound and video in enhancing learning.

Objectives of the study

- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on gender towards CAI programmes.
- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on academic qualification towards CAI programmes.
- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on professional qualification towards CAI programmes.
- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on average age towards CAI programmes.
- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on teaching experience towards CAI programmes.
- To study the significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on exposure of computers towards CAI programmes.

Hypotheses of the study

H1: There is no significant difference in the attitudes of teachers based on gender towards CAI programmes.

H2: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on academic qualification towards CAI programmes.

H3: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on professional qualification towards CAI programmes.

H4: There is no significant difference in the attitude of

teachers based on average age towards CAI programmes.

H5: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on teaching experience towards CAI programmes.

H6: There is no significant difference in the attitude of teachers based on exposure of computers towards CAI programmes.

Methodology

Survey technique as described in Best (1989) and Koul (1984) was adopted for knowing the attitude of teachers towards use of CAI. *It (Survey) requires expert and imaginative planning, careful analysis and interpretation of the data gathered, and logical and skilful reporting of the findings Best(1989).* Present study formed was actually part of the experimental study conducted to know impact of CAI programmes. All the teachers were part of the study and had good knowledge of CAI methodology.

A sample of 30 secondary school teachers from two districts each of Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh were part of the UGC-MRP study for knowing 'Impact of Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) on Underachievers in Science at Selected Urdu Medium Secondary Schools of Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh' formed sample the study.

Description of the tools used

The investigators developed a five-point attitude scale in the form of opinionnaire consisting of 35 items. The items were arranged from strongly agree to strongly disagree and corresponding scores ranged from 4 to 0 respectively for each of the item. Theoretically maximum of 140 and minimum of 0 scores could be obtained by an individual for 35 items.

Statistical Techniques Used

For the analysis of data, the investigators referred Garrett (1986), and used simple statistical techniques such as Mean, Standard Deviation and t-test. The calculations were made using data analysis from MS Excel.

Analysis and Interpretations

Table 1 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of Gender (male & female); educational qualification (Bachelor & Masters) and professional qualification (Bachelor & Masters)

Variable		Mean	Variance	Observations	Pooled Variance	Hypothesized Mean Difference	df	t Stat	P(T<=t) two-tail	t Critical two-tail
Gender	Male	62.63	29.7	8	120.98	0	28	-	0.41	2.05
	Female	66.45	151.4	22				0.8*		
Academic Qualification	Bachelor	63.45	81	20	115.62	0	28	-	0.16	2.05
	Master	69.4	188.71	10				1.4*		
Profession Qualification	Bachelor	66.04	124.04	27	120.53	0	28	-	0.37	2.05
	Master	60	75	3				0.9*		

* not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 1 indicates that the t Stat for male and female is 0.8 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.41; t-stat for Bachelor and Master degree academic qualification is 1.4 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.16 and t-stat for Bachelor and Master degree professional qualification is 0.37 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.9 are all less

than the t Critical two-tail values. Hence, the null hypotheses H1, H2, H3 are accepted.

To test the hypothesis H4, the data of was subjected to ANOVA test. The scores were obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 2.

Table 2 Anova: Single Factor of teachers based on different age groups regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

SUMMARY						
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance		
20-30 years	12	871	72.58	177.54		
30-40 years	10	610	61.00	45.11		
40-50 years	8	482	60.25	12.79		
ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	1024.95	2	512.47	5.65**	0.01	3.35
Within Groups	2448.42	27	90.68			
Total	3473.37	29				

** Significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 2 indicates that the calculated F-value is 5.65 for P value of 0.01, which is more than F Crit value of 3.35. Therefore, the null

hypothesis H4 is rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the opinions of the teachers based on different age groups (20-30, 30-40, 40-50

years) regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme. That is the teachers with three different age groups (20-30,30-40, 40-50 years) possessed different opinions regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.

Therefore, further analysis was required to determine difference between three different groups. Hence, the data was subjected to further analysis using t-test, by using two groups at a time. The analyses are given in the table below.

Table 3 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of different age groups (20-30, 30-40; 20-30, 40-50; 30-40, 40-50 years)

	Mean	Variance	Observations	Pooled Variance	Hypothesized Mean Difference	df	t Stat	P(T<=t) two-tail	t Critical two-tail
20-30 years	72.58	177.54	12	118	0	20	2.49**	0.02	2.09
30-40 years	61	45.11	10						
20-30 years	72.58	177.54	12	113.5	0	18	2.54**	0.02	2.1
40-50 years	60.3	12.8	8						
30-40 years	61	45.11	10	30.97	0	16	0.28*	0.78	2.12
40-50 years	60.3	12.8	8						

* not significant at 0.05 level, ** significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 3 indicates that the t Stat for 20-30 years and 30-40 years of age groups is 2.49 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.02 (more than t Critical two-tail); t-stat for 20-30 years and 40-50 years is 2.54 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.02 (more than t Critical two-tail) and t-stat for 30-40 years and 40-50 years of age is 0.28 for P(T<=t) two-tail at 0.78 (less than t Critical two-tail). Hence, it is concluded that 20-30 years age group respondents differ that of the 30-40, and 40-50 years of age, and the mean score

tilts in favour youngest age group in both the case as they have more positive attitude than those with more age. However, there is no significant difference in the other two senior groups.

To test the hypothesis (H5), having data from 4 variables groups the data of was subjected to ANOVA test. The scores of respondents based on years of teaching experience was obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 4.

Table 4 Anova: Single Factor of teachers based on years of teaching experience regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

SUMMARY							
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>			
7 years or less	14	965	68.93	190.84			
07-15 years	10	638	63.80	64.40			
15-25 years	4	234	58.50	3.67			
above 25 years	2	126	63.00	0.00			
ANOVA							
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>	
Between Groups	401.84	3	133.95	1.13*	0.35	2.98	
Within Groups	3071.53	26	118.14				
Total	3473.37	29					

* not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 4 indicates that the calculated F-value is 1.13 for P value of 0.35, which is less than F Crit value of 2.98. Therefore, the null hypothesis H5 is accepted. This means that there is no significant difference between the attitudes of the teachers based on years of teaching (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years) regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme. That is the teachers with four groups of

teachers with different years of teaching experience (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years, above 25 years) possessed similar attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.

To test this hypothesis (H6), the data of was subjected to t-test. The scores of teachers with slight exposure and those who had rigorous training of computers were obtained, analysed and are presented in the table 5.

Table 5 t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances of computer experience of teachers regarding their opinion towards effectiveness of CAI

	<i>slight exposure</i>	<i>rigorous training</i>
Mean	65.88	63.20
Variance	117.03	158.70
Observations	25	5
Pooled Variance	122.98	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	28	
t Stat	0.49*	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.63	
t Critical two-tail	2.05	

* not significant at 0.05 level

The analysis of data in table 5 indicates that the t Stat is 0.49 for $P(T \leq t)$ two-tail at 0.63, which is less than t Critical two-tail value of 2.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted and there is no significant difference between the teachers having slight exposure or rigorous training with regard to their attitude towards CAI.

Findings of the study

- The male and female teachers possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
- The teachers with bachelor or masters degree educational qualification possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
- The teachers with bachelor or masters degree professional qualification possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
- The teachers with three different age groups (20-30, 30-40, 40-50 years) possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
 - The teachers with 20-30 years age and 30-40 years of age possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
 - The teachers with 20-30 years age and 40-50 years of age possessed different attitudes regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
 - The teachers with 30-40 years age and 40-50 years of age possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.
- The teachers with four groups of teachers with different years of teaching experience (7 years or less, 07-15 years, 15-25 years, above 25

years) possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.

- The teachers having slight exposure and rigorous training of computer possessed similar attitude regarding effectiveness of computer assisted instruction programme.

Suggestion for further research

The study was limited to the teachers involved in the UGC-MRP project undertaken by the investigators. It may be extended beyond this limited group. The study may be undertaken by involving primary, higher primary; government, private; rural, urban; different mediums of teachers etc. The teachers may be encouraged to develop and test their own software.

Conclusion

The computer assisted instruction programmes are very systematic, organised, interesting form of instruction. These programmes due to contemporary content and use of multi-media potentialities have very good potential for education children specifically underachieving children. We cannot think of programmes without the help of teachers, where as these programmes can be supplementary to the classroom teaching.

References

1. Best Kahn (1989), Research in Education, New Delhi, Prentice Hall of India, New Delhi
2. Koul L. (1984) Methodology of Education research, New Delhi, Vikas Publishing House.
3. Garrett Henry E., Statistics in Psychology and Education, Vishal Publishers, Pvt. Limited, New Delhi
4. Garrett, H.E. (1986) – Statistics in Psychology and Education, Vikils Feffers and Simmons Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai
